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Political economy of agrarian change: A synoptic view of rural transformation in Manipur

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The study of agrarian change is of fundamental importance; whether one is analyzing political change or the agricultural change or change in social institutions and values. There has been a great hiatus between the image of the agrarian social structure in the minds of the political elite and the actual reality of the agrarian society. This gap, now, is a serious factor that hinders the radical social transformation. In Manipur, planners of today have not ruminated towards the institutional approach to ameliorate rural change and development. However, knowledge of the agrarian structure should play an important part in determining any strategy for rural development. Agricultural involution and marginalization of landholdings has been increasing due to increasing population pressure and inability of absorbing increasing labour force by the tertiary sector. This paper shows the present scenario of the economy of Manipur as well as the

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transformation of rural economy from the historical native period. Moreover, it also highlights the emergence of new middle class and government's apathy to transform rural economy.

Introduction:

Manipur was a surplus generating agrarian economy in pre- British period. In the 13th century, the Italian writers had the knowledge of this region. The capital of Manipur was one of the forty-nine major cities of Asia in the works of geography published in the 18th and 19th century. The nation was recorded as an independent kingdom or occasionally as a part of Burmese empire according to her political status. Although the topography of the kingdom was recorded as early as the 17th century by the Europeans, the history of Manipur was silent until Captain Robert Baker gave a stray account of the conquest of Manipur by the Burmese king Alaungpaya.(Wangam, 2016). The Treaty of Yandaboo (1826) was signed between Burma and Britain and Manipur was declared independent. A British Political Agency was opened in 1835. It is the period between the opening of the British Political Agency and the Anglo-Manipur war of 1891 that we call the Native Period of which the economy and agrarian structure is analyzed.(Chongtham, 2005a). The study of the agrarian social structure is a study of groups connected with land. Since land constitute the chief basis of productive activity in the rural society, the formation of groups is primarily connected with the differentiation of rights over land. This is only the first step in the construction of adequate view of the agrarian social structure (Joshi, 1969). As reported by Howell, the cultivated land in the valley was categorized into nine types, viz: i) Tauna Lou ii) Pham Lou iii) Sepoy Lou iv) Mana Lou v) Brahmin Lou vi) Temple Lou vii) Maharani Lou viii) Royal Family Lou ix) Raja's Lou.

When Manipur merged with the Indian Union in 1949, the economy of Manipur plunged into the lap of centrally planned economy. During the status of Union Territory up to 1972, nothing was done in Manipur to improve productive base. While India imported practically no consumer goods since 1960s, the state economy was dependent more and more on the mainland economy for food

grains and other goods. In the context of the Indian economy, economic liberalization imposed drastic structural change in the state economy of Manipur exacerbating the already feeble economy. View with compartmentalization shows that in the post-liberalization phase, neither agriculture nor industry becomes the accelerator of the economy. The population of Manipur as per 2011 census was 28.56 lakhs comprising 14.39 lakhs of male and 14.17 lakhs female. In major parts of the population of Manipur, voluntary organizations is now playing a very important role to accelerate the development of education sector thereby focusing more on white-collar jobs. The structure that humans create to order their political/economic environment is the basic determinant of the performance of an economy. It provides the incentives which shape the choice humans make. The dominant beliefs of political and economic entrepreneurs construct an elaborate structure of institutions that determine economic and political performance. The ideology and vision embedded in the verisimilitude development strategy of the state government is highly related to the substructure of the state economy. Policies of economic liberalization initiated since 1990s created a new middle class that shifted their role, attitude, lifestyles and consumption practice from that of traditional elites in colonial rule. In the context of Manipur, with increasing educational development the rural population existing in the middle class has been demanding employment in the tertiary sector, especially in the government jobs in order to have social deferent. This reflects the sign of vehement concept, “hegemony” as introduced by Antonio Gramsci. Therefore, it is imperative to understand the agrarian structure and its transformation.

Transformation and trajectory of Manipur’s economy:

Manipur was a surplus generating agrarian economy in pre-British period. After Anglo-Manipur War of 1891, the colonial rule brought about structural change in the economy having a subservient position to British India. Introduction of strong institutions i.e., private property in land, monetization of economy along with commercialization of agriculture and taxation strengthened the colonial grip of Manipur by the British. When Manipur merged with the Indian Union in 1949, the economy of Manipur plunged into the lap of centrally planned economy. During the regime of Nehru, an institutional approach for agricultural

development was introduced as an important part and parcel of his overall planning strategy (Ashutosh, 1998a). In the development trajectory of the Indian economy,

it was transformed into liberalized economy since 1991. The pre-liberalization economy of the state may be divided into two phases- first, a centralized economy of pre-statehood period and second, post-statehood economy phases up to 1991. The first four five-year plans during the pre-statehood period of Manipur's economy was concentrated more on transport and communication as well as social and community services thereby neglecting the vital sectors of the economy i.e., agriculture, industry, irrigation and power. In Manipur, Community Development Programme (CDP) was also introduced when it was a Union Territory as CDP was launched in 1952 all across India for the development of the countryside (Oinam, 2008). Thus, the two sectors viz. transport and communication and social and community services accounted for 91, 73, 77 and 66 percent of the total outlay in the first four plan period respectively. It reflects the economy of Manipur after merger, a peripheral economy as India's economic planning favoured mainland India while the periphery economy remained isolated from the development matrix of the country in the initial stage of planning. During the Lal Bahadur Shastri's regime, Subramaniam, Food and Agricultural Ministry, tried to adopt new agricultural strategy through a pilot basis by selecting 1000 agricultural plots with good irrigation and by supplying fertilizers and distributing 200 tons of wheat, imported from Mexico, to that selected lands (Ashutosh, 1998b). Notwithstanding, nothing was done in Manipur during the centralized planning to strengthen the productive base of the economy. The state was in existence as a captive market for the indigenous capitalist class of India. In the development debate, investigations in political economy consist in isolating the specific modes and the relationships of dominance and dependency that exist at various points in the socio-historico and cultural process (Griffin, 1968, Frank, 1969). In the case of North-East India, it can be imbricated within a metropole satellite relationship that subsists in the Indian capital and the Indian state (Rafiul and Prasenjit, 2004). Since mid 1960s, India imported practically no consumer goods. However, the period also witnessed increasing dependence of the state economy on the mainland economy for food grains and other consumer goods. When Manipur got statehood in 1972, some

changes were seen in the development approach of the state economy. The state started giving attention on agriculture and industry focusing on major irrigation projects and establishment of Public Sector Undertakings (PSUs). The first major irrigation project, Loktak Lift Irrigation Project was taken up in the year 1973-74. It was followed by medium river irrigation projects and minor irrigation projects. After Manipur attained statehood the agricultural scenario witnessed a modest participation of the Green Revolution. Fisher- Clark hypothesis state that with economic advancement, the service sector employment will increase first due to decline in the share of employment in agriculture and next to fall in the share in manufacturing. This hypothesis is found prevailing in Manipur. However, in Manipur the trend of raising employment from agriculture to services is not due to economic advancement. It is mainly due to the fact that the state economy survives as a captive market for the mainland capitalist and people's preference tends to incline more on social deferent. The industrialization process was not able to absorb the growing workforce from the primary sector owing to inherent weakness of the industrialization and structural constraints.

In the context of the Indian economy, economic liberalization imparted drastic structural change exacerbating the already feeble economy. View with compartmentalization shows that in the post-liberalization phase, neither agriculture nor industry becomes the accelerator of the state economy. Because of the fact that, heightened tertiarisation is the order of the day in the post liberalization phase. Liberalization has resulted in the increase of unemployment rate and marginalization of labor force. The non-workers have increased by 31% and marginal workers have registered a mammoth increase of 39%. Why is labor force moving out of agriculture in Manipur? It is not due to more productive or more attractive alternatives but they find less incentive in agriculture (Hanjabam, 2012a). It highlights the dissatisfaction of the farmers with their profession and their uncertain future. Moreover, as more social class values tend to increase in the new modern society, people desire to have social deferent. Liberalization has resulted in accelerating influx of agricultural goods at too low a price which strengthen the less incentive to the farmers in the state.

The Indo-Myanmar Border Trade was officially launched in 12th April 1995 as a corollary to India's economic liberalization. According to official data, goods worth Rs. 31,70,51,137 were exported when the import volume was Rs. 15,17,64,137 during 1996-97 but it dwindled to just Rs. 5,64,45,050 in export and Rs. 5,00,81,749 in import (Sangai Express, 1st August 2006, Imphal). It is estimated that in 2004-05, goods amounting to Rs. 186 crores were estimated to be imported from Myanmar through informal trade (Thongam, 2008). Agricultural goods constitute only 14.09% of the total annual imports from Myanmar amounting to a total of Rs. 121.90 crores in 2010. Manipur being a rice deficit state, Myanmar's surplus rice products at comparatively cheaper prices finds ready market in all corners of the state. The burgeoning imports from Myanmar along with imports from mainland India have significantly crippled the fledging productive units in Manipur. On the other hand, there are limitless opportunities in border trade as well as international trade but uncontrolled and ill directed trade has also bottomless pitfalls such as rising inequity, suffocating of home production and risky dependence on international stability (Chongtham, 2005b).

Agrarian Structure: Its historical roots

A British Political Agency was opened in 1835. It is the period between the opening of the British Political Agency and the Anglo-Manipur war of 1891 that we call the Native Period of which the economy and agrarian structure is analyzed. (Chongtham, 2005c). The study of the agrarian social structure is a study of groups connected with land. Since land constitute the chief basis of productive activity in the rural society, the formation of groups is primarily connected with the differentiation of rights over land. This is only the first step in the construction of adequate view of the agrarian social structure (Joshi, 1969b). As reported by Howell, the cultivated land in the valley was categorized into nine types, viz: i) Tauna Lou ii) Pham Lou iii) Sepoy Lou iv) Mana Lou v) Brahmin Lou vi) Temple Lou vii) Maharani Lou viii) Royal Family Lou ix) Raja's Lou. During the Native Rule, no lease or patta of any kind was issued to the landholders and there was no legal protection of the tenants. The fertility of the valley of Manipur was due to seasonal flooding. The population of the valley at the beginning of the Native

Period had sufficient and surplus arable fertile land for subsistence living. The whole art of utilizing the water resources of the river and lakes were developed at this period as to imply Proto-Hydraulic Civilization by the 1st century A.D. (Arambam Lokendra, Meitei Cultural History). The two river system- Imphal River and Iril River was regularly dredged for communication and transport as well as for irrigation. The efficiency of food production as reported by Brown estimated that yields of paddy *per parea* were 100 baskets (2700 kg) even in the worst land. Though Population had risen to 65,000 by 1873 from 20,000 in 1835, Brown estimated that one year's produce was enough to feed the population for two years. According to Pamberton, Manipur traded with China; the Chinese took away wax, ivory, clothes, cotton and ponies from Manipur. Salt product being the property of the king, were manned by Lois, who were settled near the salt wells. Silk culture was also entirely entrusted to the Lois of the population. In 1873, only five villages of the West and Northwest foothills of the valley reared silk worms. Only 300 workers were reported employed in the silk culture in 1873 in those five villages (Chongtham, 2005d).

The Loi population played a vital role in the manufacturing sector of the native economy. Silk manufacturer, iron smelters, distillers of spirit, the makers of earthen vessels, salt manufacturer etc. were strategically placed in the periphery of the valley where non-farm resources of the economy could be economically exploited. Iron smelters of Kakching produced iron in the Southeast, Lois of Sugnu extracted forest wealth of the South and neighbouring Burma in the extreme South. Lois of Thanga produced fishes from Loktak, the salt manufacturer in the extreme northeast, the silk manufactures in the extreme Northeastern foothills and the spirit distillers of Sekmai in the extreme north of the valley, all these Loi villages surrounded the bowels of the valley producing the rice economy. According to Brown, all descendants of the lowest castes were consigned to the Lois. This class of people represented the lowest rung of society and their role in the feudal set up was crucial in many ways. Even though Manipur's economy was highly transformed from autarky position to open economy during British rule, only low level of trade was seen due to many reasons. Lack of proper roads connecting the valley to the neighbouring countries was the bottleneck to trade. The Aqai Route, Kala Naga Route, and the Khongjai Route

connected Manipur to Cachar valley. However, the first and the last routes had become almost non-functional in the early 19th century. Sekmai, Heirok and Imole routes were essentially bridle paths imposing heavy hardship for travelers. By emphasizing more on institutional hurdles that hindered tertiary and manufacturing sectors, Lallup was one such institution (Chongtham, 2005e). For the administration of Lallup, the population was divided into four panas such as Khabam, Laipham, Ahallup and Naharup. The panas performed lallup or forced labour for 10 days in every forty (N. Ibohi, 1968). Only the Loi population of the fishing community was exempted from lallup duty. As the monetization of the economy was in rudimentary form, collection of tax revenue was mainly based on kind rather than money based. Even land revenue was collected in kind as most other revenues. Manipur's economy by the nature of trade and manufacture described above was therefore a classic peasant economy based on agriculture which would be perhaps similar to Schultz's Traditional Agriculture in the sense that factors of production were constantly used through generations. In the agrarian economy of Manipur during 1891, those landowners who owned Mana Lou and Pham Lou of 19.6 parea of land could be considered as the landed gentry, the class of landlords in the sense that the Raja's favourites and awardees of Mana Lou held 15 pareas of land per person, and the state officials held 6.4 pareas per person (Chongtham, 2005f). Focusing on the production relation, the king collected the heaviest rent on the land for the king by the slaves. The slaves paid 50% of the produce as rent and the peasant supplied the plough cattle and implements to the slaves. This may be perhaps the picture of sharecropping tenancy as was seen in many parts of India. However, the feature of rack renting that strongly existed in colonial India was not seen in Manipur as rent paid to the state or landowners ranged between 1% and 6% on the best land and 2% to 12% on the worst land. The land tenure system in Manipur could not be called oppressive or exploitative if rent is a criterion.

Agrarian Change: Entering into the Tertiary sector

In the absence of industrialization and the strengthening of the agrarian base of Manipur, fast population growth has led to land hunger, agricultural involution and massive occupational diversification into the tertiary sector, which has been

fed by huge investments in the unproductive sector. The landownership pattern based on recent findings of village level surveys in the most productive district of the Manipur valley shows that intergeneration transfers and subdivisions have resulted in extremely small landholdings without any visible sign of capitalistic land accumulation or polarization. In Wabagai Village, land ownership of an average size of 0.61 acres constitutes 30.13% of landholdings, while another 31.17% is composed of landholdings of 1.24 acres. The most important basis for inequality is the distribution of land with which leisure, enjoyment of status and authorities are associated (Myrdal 1968). In the economy of Manipur, small and marginal holders dominate in the size distribution of land and the medium and large holders are virtually disappearing. Historical dynamics and structural evolution of the economy have led to agricultural involution and marginalization of ownership as well as operational holdings, without any visible sign of an agrarian capitalist class. In Wabagai village, about 92% of landholdings are marginal and small in terms of average size. In the agricultural sector, the lease market has been strengthened by the circumstances of demand and supply side. In the rural sector, especially in the valley, there has been huge competition among the landless to lease in even the smallest piece of paddy land at least to provide for subsistence paddy and create the safety net for the extreme levels of uncertainties in other casual employment. In Wabagai village, 62.51% of the households do not own land. It reflects the sign of land hunger in rural sector. While the fixed kind- rent type of tenure relationship between the lesser and lessee in Manipur had remained in the post-colonial period, the agricultural census data began to record usufruct mortgage type of tenure arrangements. In the mortgage tenancy arrangement, the mortgagee pays no interest on cash given to the landowner during the pendency of the debt. The mortgagee can cultivate the land or lease it out to others and receive rent from the cultivator. Once the debt is cleared between the lesser and lessee, the land reverts to the owner. This type of tenure is now significantly emerging in many villages. Sickness, children's education and social ceremonies, like marriages and mortuary rites, as well as the euphoria of social deferent are some of the prime reasons for mortgaging out land (Chongtham & Hanjabam, 2013a).

Poor irrigation infrastructure is a main obstacle for the development of agrarian economy of the state. The state is still heavily dependent on monsoon for agriculture purpose. The state government is also reluctant to invest for capital formation in agriculture. Deformity in irrigation not only discourages double and multiple cropping but also severely affects the use of HYVs. Notwithstanding, assuring efficient irrigation through collective community action has been at the core of cropping intensity and crop diversification in Wabagai village. In the last decade, the village has found its own alternative way in water management and resource conservation and expansion. In the lean winter season, villagers dammed up the Sekmai River and ensured irrigation to the vital cash crops. Local Clubs and NGOs have also stepped in to help for providing lift and pump irrigation. In developing countries, communities are defined by groups of people tied by mutual trust, based on intense personal relationships, and take forms like tribes and villages tied by blood and local affinities. In these communities, especially of the Southeast Asian types, principles of mutual help, income and work-sharing for generating subsistence to all members are strong and economic rationality in terms of individual profit and utility maximization does not operate in a community of this definition (Hayami and Godo 2005:328). The small intensive farming under cooperative behaviour and collective action has not been widely practiced in Manipur. Instead, growth and development in Wabagai village, is based on running efficient small farms under cooperative behaviour and collective action. Further, high degree of self-employment only shows how villagers are striving towards survival autonomy. 70.35% of the entire population of Wabagai village are living as self-employed. Culled from many issues which forestall the strengthening of agrarian base thereby afflicting the survival autonomy of villages, lacking irrigation facilities in most part of the agrarian base of Manipur is a major issue that hinders the sprout of survival autonomy of most of the villages. Market is also an important factor that can accelerate the production of agriculture output. Emphasizing the changing cropping patterns in agricultural sector of Manipur, crop diversification tends to increase at Kakching, Wabagai and Kakching Khunou where irrigation facilities are somewhat better. Durkheim's Modernisation Theory claimed that advances in communication and transport technology brought isolated communities together with profound consequences. As communications and transportation brought people into closer

proximity, people lost the ability to survive on their own and became dependent on each other- this was “organic solidarity” of modern society (Hass, 2007). The fear of market for the products produced by Kakching, Wabagai and Kakching Khunou were reduced because of the increasing mobility of people amongst neighbouring villages and changing cultural factors.

The population of Manipur as per 2011 census was 28.56 lakhs comprising 14.39 lakhs of males and 14.17 lakhs of females. Population of Manipur constitutes nearly 0.24% of the total population of India. In the agriculture sector, 52.81% of the workers in Manipur are engaged as cultivators and agricultural labours. The total number of educational institutions (schools, colleges, universities) in the state during the year 2002-03 stood at 4284 showing an increase of 2.41% over that of the previous year (Economic Survey, Manipur, 2015-16). In major parts of rural population of Manipur, voluntary organizations now play a very important role to accelerate the development of education sectors thereby focusing on the white-collar jobs. For instance, Kakching Khunou Educational Forum has been working since 2012 to uplift the community of Kakching Khunou, focusing on the service sector. As a consequence, it creates a positive externality in the neighbouring villages. This leads to rapid increase in demand for government jobs, as Kakching town also has been endeavouring with success to uplift Kakching population through voluntary organizations.

State’s apathy to transform rural economy:

Marx viewed reality as a rich totality of interpenetrating events and relationships. The dialectical approach also embraces a particular epistemology. Knowledge is produced dialectically in this view by the act of enquiry in shaping reality as well as discovering knowledge. Doing and thinking are fundamentally related to each other, forming praxis. Once superstructure is created, the elements may follow a path of development divorced from the material circumstances in which they were borne and may even influence the material substructure of society (Charles, 2004). It is already known that the economy of Manipur is in the form of captive market and tertiarization has been increasing as the state government also invests more on this sector. According to Douglass North, the structure that humans

create to order their political/economic environment is the basic determinant of the performance of an economy. It provides the incentives which shape the choice humans make. The dominant beliefs of political and economic entrepreneurs construct an elaborate structure of institutions that determine economic and political performance. The ideology and vision embedded in the verisimilitude development strategy of the state government is highly related to the substructure of the state economy. Policies of economic liberalization initiated since 1990s have been accompanied by an array of visual images and public discourses that have centred on a shifting role of the middle class and their attitudes, lifestyles and consumption practices. For example, popular stories, advertising images, Cell phones, rising wage levels for the managerial staff of MNCs, cars, washing machine and colour TVs have produced an image of the rise of an emerging middle-class culture in India. These representations have identified the rise of this new middle class with the success of economic reform (Fernandes, 2006a). During colonial period in India, this social group is characterized by specific kinds of socio-economic resources such as access to English education and modern forms of professional employment. As a result, such social group arose which are different from Traditional elites in the sense that the cultural life of this middle class had deviated from the cultural life of traditional elites. This led to the dependence of the middle class on the colonial state (Fernandes, 2006b). In the context of Manipur, with increasing educational development, the rural population existing in the upper class has been demanding employment in the Tertiary sector, especially in the Govt. job in order to have social deferent. On the other hand, India's decentralization is similar with the political system during British Raj, and India's federal system is "Holding Together" federation, under which charismatic leaders of India's freedom movement framed the constitution, for they were suspicious of further partition (Mukherjee, 1989 & Raghunandan, 2013). As the life of the state government highly depends on the central government, even this middle class, which emerged in the economy of Manipur, have strengthened the state government thereby neglecting the importance of primary productive base. This reflects the sign of vehement concept "hegemony" as introduced by Antonio Gramsci. The present writer concludes that if India's

centralization continues to persist, even the democratic election will accelerate political hegemony. Therefore, it is imperative to understand the agrarian structure and its transformation.

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